

ISW

In Silico World: Lowering barriers to ubiquitous adoption of In Silico Trials
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Executive Summary

The objective of In Silico World (ISW) project is to lower a number of barriers that slow down the adoption of in silico trial technologies. Among the various barriers, **poorly informed stakeholders continue to remain a stumbling block in the awareness and adoption of in silico technologies** within the healthcare systems. To alleviate this problem, there is a growing need for comprehensive information and education materials for all involved stakeholders, such as regulators, patients, healthcare professionals, etc.

Healthcare professionals (HCPs) that encompass both medical practitioners and those from allied healthcare professions like imaging technologists, are cornerstone stakeholders for in silico technologies, as they act as champions, gatekeepers and end-users of the in silico solutions. The preliminary policy brief (D5.5. Policy Brief) from ISW project acknowledged challenges associated with engaging and empowering HCPs. It **recommended the creation and delivery of tailored information packages for HCPs**, which bundle useful information and resources like self-reading introductory material, glossaries, case studies, success stories, etc. and accredited lecture materials to **empower healthcare professionals to familiarize themselves with and adopt in silico trial technologies**.

This deliverable presents **ready-to-use three information packages** and one set of **lecture materials**. They are set to offer basic understanding, awareness for medical students as well as healthcare professionals, who are new to in silico technologies. They are consciously presented in layman's terms, to lower the barrier of understanding for non-technical readers. The packages and lecture materials presented as individual chapters, which can be used as *standalone materials for self-reading and/or to steer professionals peer-to-peer discussions on in silico trial technologies*. **The lecture materials are offered through e-learning platform**, whereby groups of HCPs or individuals can self-enrol themselves. These introductory lectures are structured into three modules with comprehensive example cases from ISW project.

The packages assimilated in this deliverable are meant to offer not only impactful information around in silico medicine and in silico technologies, but also introduce HCPs to continuous education programs. Thus, offer **opportunity to deepen their knowledge for professional practice**, whereby the mutual understanding and collaboration between the in silico community and HCPs can be strengthened.

1 Introduction

The rapidly evolving field of in silico medicine, is where computer modelling and simulations are increasingly used to understand, diagnose, treat, or even prevent diseases. The objective of In Silico World (ISW) project is to **lower a number of barriers that slow down the adoption of in silico trial technologies**. In silico trials are the use of modelling and simulation technologies to evaluate the safety or the efficacy of new drugs and medical devices. Despite the huge potential of these technologies, their adoption is still very slow because there are several barriers: educational, regulatory, cultural, and technological. The goal is to **accelerate the uptake of modelling and simulation technologies for the development and regulatory assessment of medicines and medical devices** with a long-term impact of reduction of the cost and duration of the development and regulatory assessment of new medical products while maintaining or improving the level of safety provided by conventional approaches.

The project aims at addressing the **most important barriers to the uptake of in silico trials** (see Figure 1), namely: (1) lack of advanced models; (2) lack of independent validation collections; (3) poorly informed stakeholders; (4) lack of clear regulatory pathways; (5) poor scalability and efficiency; (6) need for viable business models and, (7) lack of trained workforce.

Figure 1: Barriers to in silico trials

Among the various barriers, **poorly informed stakeholders** continue to remain a **stumbling block in the awareness and adoption of in silico technologies within the healthcare systems**. To alleviate this problem, there is a growing need for comprehensive information and education materials for all involved stakeholders, such as regulators, patients, healthcare professionals, etc. This continues to be the core focus of work packages (WP) WP5 and WP7 of the ISW project, whereby **information packages (in WP5) and educational materials (in WP7) are tailor-made for individual stakeholder groups** and the wider community. To support these initiatives, various surveys, questionnaires, focus

group sessions were conducted. They provided key learnings and threw light on the critical themes to address through information packages and lecture materials, both to inform stakeholders but also to empower them with tangible examples, use cases and success stories around in silico technologies.

For instance, one of the WP5 activities includes the creation of a dynamic info kit for modellers – ***'The in silico medicine INFOKIT'***¹ (shown in Figure 2), to facilitate effective engagement of modellers with all other involved stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, patients, regulators, etc. Likewise, WP7 has identified the key competences and learning objectives - ***'Intended learning Objectives for in silico trials'***² (shown in Figure 2). The definition of intended learning objectives (ILO), further led to curation of lecture materials and pilot courses that interdisciplinary stakeholders of in silico technology would benefit from.

Figure 2: 'In silico medicine INFOKIT' and 'Learning goals for in silico trials'

Scope

While the various information packages and lecture materials developed within the ISW project are catering to all in silico stakeholder groups, this deliverable focuses only on the materials targeting healthcare professionals. By **healthcare professionals (HCP)**, we refer to both **medical doctors and allied professionals**, with bachelor of science (BS) and master of science (MS) degree in medicine as well as those with advanced master's degree in non-medical clinical degrees like imaging technologist. They can be students or experienced healthcare professionals, who seek to gain introduction and professional knowledge around in silico trial technologies.

In the following sub-sections, we first highlight the **critical role of HCPs**, the **existing gaps and challenges** associated with **engaging and empowering healthcare professionals**, within the realm of in silico medicine. Subsequently, in chapters 2 and 3 of this deliverable, we address some of these challenges through **information packages for HCPs (chapter 2)** and **lecture materials for HCPs (chapter 3)**, tailored to the needs of healthcare professionals.

¹Contin, M., Montesarchio, D., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lesage, R., Platanov, A., Goran, S., De Michele, R., Rangarajan, J.R., Geris, L. An in silico medicine Info kit for effective stakeholder engagement (2024). VPH Conference 2024 – Sep4-6, 2024, Stuttgart, Germany.

² Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380239>.

1.1 Health care professionals (HCPs) as key stakeholders

Figure 3 illustrates the stakeholders relevant for the uptake of in silico trial technologies, as identified and reported within the In Silico World Project^{3,4}. Among these various stakeholders of in silico medicine, **healthcare professionals** in particular have an important role to play in the progression of the field, as they serve as a **vital bridge between the research realm and the wider community**⁵.

HCPs as medical practitioners

Often trusted sources of information for the general public, **HCPs act as intermediaries, communicating the benefits, as well as limitations of novel technologies to their patients**, making technical information accessible. Without their acceptance and endorsement, uptake in the clinic would lack, thus, collaboration and engagement with HCPs is essential⁵.

Figure 3: Stakeholders of in silico trials technologies

HCPs as key cornerstones of in silico technologies

The healthcare professionals are the cornerstones for in silico technologies, in many ways. Though often seen as medical practitioners who use in silico technologies to treat, inform and engage with patients, their inputs, contributions, and roles are pivotal across the entire healthcare ecosystem. Starting from **identifying an unmet clinical need** that leads to the **co-development of solutions in collaboration with in silico technology developers**, they are also key **gatekeepers who critically**

³ ISW, WP5 – T5.3 Stakeholder engagement – Milestone MS13 report.

⁴ Van Oudheusden, M., Lesage, R., and Van Hoyweghen, I. Delphi Survey: Analysis of Results after Round 1, 2022. Available on ISW SharePoint.

⁵ Winter, P., & Carusi, A. (2022). 'If You're Going to Trust the Machine, Then That Trust Has Got to Be Based on Something': Validation and the Co-Constitution of Trust in Developing Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the Early Diagnosis of Pulmonary Hypertension (PH). *Science & Technology Studies*, 35(4), 58–77. <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.102198> (Original work published March 22, 2022).

review and assess the in silico technologies for their safety, efficacy and effectiveness. By adopting the market-approved technologies in their clinical practice, HCPs become end users that harness the value of in silico technology for the benefit of patients and wider society. As a true cornerstone of reference for the healthcare system, HCPs also facilitate monitoring the real-world use of in silico technologies to flag regulators and developers, while also addressing questions and concerns of patients. This collective contribution of HCPs, be it for development, assessment or adoption, **guides market approval decisions by regulators, reimbursement decisions by payers** of the healthcare systems, as well as policy makers to draft and **monitor healthcare policies**. Overall, **healthcare professionals are champions and guard the doors for community acceptance**.

It has been noted that the actual uptake of in silico technologies amongst HCPs in clinics, as well as in regulatory and technology assessment agencies, remains low⁷. To this end, efforts to increase awareness and knowledge about in silico technologies are essential for **building and maintaining trust among the healthcare professional community**, ensuring informed decision-making, and fostering confidence in the integration of computational methods into medical practice⁶.

1.2 Gaps and challenges for HCPs

The ISW project envisioned the critical role of healthcare professionals in the context of in silico medicine and drafted a series of strategies and specific channels to engage and empower this stakeholder group. To begin with, various WP5 stakeholder activities like surveys, interviews, focus group discussions of ISW project involved engagements with clinicians. These revealed many gaps and specific needs of the healthcare professionals, especially in the context of familiarization with and adoption of the in silico technologies. In this section, we first summarise the key gaps, as noted in our engagement activities:

Lack of awareness and familiarity

Clinicians participating in the 2021 VPHi survey on the uptake of CM&S in clinic⁷, exhibited **limited awareness** on in silico terminologies and lack of familiarity in using the technology, along with a clear indication that the adoption of in silico technologies in clinics as low.

Definitional issues

Definitional issues still exist to date with different stakeholders sometimes using different terminologies to indicate similar concepts or grouping different concepts under the same term. A typical example here is the intersection of in silico medicine and artificial intelligence (AI)^{6,7}. During in silico ecosystem engagements like meetings and conferences, the in silico community repeatedly

⁶ Winter, P., & Carusi, A. (2022). 'If You're Going to Trust the Machine, Then That Trust Has Got to Be Based on Something': Validation and the Co-Constitution of Trust in Developing Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the Early Diagnosis of Pulmonary Hypertension (PH). *Science & Technology Studies*, 35(4), 58–77. <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.102198>.

⁷ Lesage, R., Van Oudheusden, M., Schievano S., Van Hoyweghen, I., Geris, L., Capelli, C. Mapping the use of computational modelling and simulation in clinics: A survey. *Front Med Technol.* 2023 Apr 17;5:1125524. doi: 10.3389/fmedt.2023.1125524. PMID: 37138727; PMCID: PMC10150234.

echoed concerns that these definitional challenges are present, which can lead to misunderstandings and oversimplifications.

Mismatched expectations

Lack of familiarity with in silico technologies, combined with the differing expectations on what is (not) possible through in silico technologies, seems to also create gaps and ambiguities for HCPs. Further, it raises questions on how the uncertainties noted during the validation of CM&S technologies are likely to impact the downstream clinical decision-making by HCPs.

Lack of trust and trustworthiness

The survey conducted with clinicians⁵ recorded high trust levels, provided that they have had a previous positive experience, despite a relatively low level of awareness. Investigating this further, social scientists studying the acceptance of in silico technologies, highlight the relational aspect of trust among individuals, emphasizing the focus on the trustworthiness of the ecosystem behind the in silico techniques^{8,9}.

Changing landscape of expertise

Healthcare professionals, who are at the forefront of adopting in silico technologies, are expected to go beyond their traditional skill set and leverage these innovations to support their clinical decision-making. While healthcare professionals grapple their roles within the regulatory and technology assessment pillars, the responsible research and innovation workshop¹⁰ organised by ISW consortium, identified the increasing **need for (re-) training HCPs, like the other involved stakeholders, in technical aspects but also on the ethical, legal, and social implications of these novel technologies**. Thus, this could imply a changing landscape of expertise that healthcare professionals are expected to accumulate and establish, much beyond the conventional act of primary care of their patients.

Lack of trained workforce across healthcare ecosystem

Acknowledging the lack of trained workforce, the ISW project envisioned to mapping the necessary competencies of various in silico stakeholders as part of its WP7 activities. In addition to training students in medical school, the **ISW consortium advocates for continued education of HCPs** on in silico technologies. Special emphasis is placed not to limit this to HCPs within the hospitals and university medical centres, but to expand the outreach to those **HCPs in regulatory agencies, health technology assessment bodies as well as governmental organization like national competent authorities and policy making**¹¹.

⁸ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., and Van Hoyweghen, I (2023). Rep. *WP5 Stakeholder Engagement - Focus Groups Analysis* Available on ISW SharePoint.

⁹ O'Doherty, K. C. (2023). Trust, trustworthiness, and relationships: ontological reflections on public trust in science. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23299460.2022.2091311>.

¹⁰ Elhadj, E., Van Horenbeeck, Z., Lievevrouw, E., and Van Hoyweghen, I (2023). Rep. *Responsible Research and Innovation Workshop Report, 2023*. Available on ISW SharePoint.

¹¹ Van Horenbeeck, Z., Rangarajan, J.R., Biasin, E., Lesage, R., Goran, S., Viceconti, M., and Geris, L (2023). 'D5.5 Policy Brief - Report based on preparatory phase of stakeholder activities – version 1- M36 – Dec 2023.

The bottom line: “Poorly informed stakeholders”

The preliminary policy brief (D5.5. Policy Brief¹¹) from the ISW project acknowledged all of the above gaps and advocated the need for information packages such as this one, bundling useful information and resources to increase HCPs understanding of in silico trials through information material, glossaries, case studies, success stories, best practices, etc. Further, the identification of learning goals and access to **training modules** on in silico medicine within the standard educational track as well as through **accredited e-learning materials**, were deemed necessary to realize the advancement of the domain.

1.3 Information package & lecture materials

The primary objective of this deliverable is to leverage the available materials to engage with HCPs in a meaningful way. To address the barriers and gaps around the lack of a trained workforce for in silico technologies, the ISW project set out to produce information packages and course modules for **training a new workforce around the development and use of in silico trial technologies**. It also included the ambition to identify stakeholders’ specific materials to re-train professionals, who are already working in the industry and governmental organisations, like regulatory agencies and health technology assessment bodies. While the former group of **technology developers** are targeted to gather **competences to innovate and develop in silico technologies**, the focus on the latter group of **allied professionals of end users and decision-makers**, is towards honing **skills for critical evaluation of the in silico technologies**¹².

1.3.1 HCPs as non-technical stakeholders

Given that healthcare professionals are at the forefront of using the in silico trial technologies in professional practice, they become the primary end-users of in silico technologies. ISW project identifies them as **non-technical stakeholders**, who would possibly need **minimal focus on modelling and simulation** itself, rather more **emphasis on the awareness, familiarity and understanding of in silico technologies** in healthcare organisations. In other words, HCPs are considered as non-technical stakeholders that foster real world adoption of the in silico technologies, whereby they need to be informed and familiar with these technologies, but more importantly also about the strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities offered by IST¹³.

The **HCPs, seen as non-technical stakeholders**, are further categorized into **students** (enrolled in bachelor/master programs within clinical or non-clinical allied discipline), or **professionals** (working

¹² Jos Vander Sloten, Giorgio Davico, Marco Viceconti (2023). D7.1 Report on ILO’s, modules and delivery models. Version 2 – Jan 26, 2023.

¹³ Briefly, the in silico technology developers (e.g. within industry, academia, hospitals, etc.) are deemed as technical stakeholders, while the members evaluating and adopting these technologies (e.g. management) within the industry, hospital or healthcare systems, as well as regulatory affairs professionals, clinicians and allied health professionals, are categorized as non-technical stakeholders. One notable exception being those HCPs active in research and innovation stream, who are co-developing in silico trial technology, are categorized both technical and non-technical category.

in medical facilities, industry, regulatory or HTA agencies), who may require training or retraining. Although both of these groups hold different levels of background expertise within their professional set-up, all HCPs often start as **beginners when it comes to the information and education on in silico trial technologies**^{14,15}.

1.3.2 Outlook: Packages and lecture materials

Considering all HCPs as beginners with regard to their awareness and knowledge about in silico technologies, **Chapter 2** first presents **three information packages on in silico technologies**, which **incrementally builds awareness and literacy on in silico technologies**. HCPs can use the materials as standalone items for self-consumption. Further, the packages can also serve as learning or **dissemination materials for peer-to-peer exchanges among fellow HCPs** be it at the university hospitals for **engaging with other non-technical stakeholders**.

Chapter 3 presents the overview of lecture materials that are tailor made for HCPs. Here again, the focus is not to dive deep to the unique needs of all subcategories of HCPs (e.g. hospital vs regulatory, vs HTA), but rather begin with **high quality foundational material** that introduces the in silico technologies through a formal course work. They are formulated as **three modules, each lasting about 2 hours of mini-self-learning courses**. It is made available through an e-learning platform, for ease of access and flexibility of HCPs, such that they can pace their learning amidst their demanding study/work schedules.

¹⁴ Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380239>.

¹⁵ Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400657>.

2 Information package for HCPs

Engaging stakeholders in innovative projects, especially in in silico medicine, offers numerous benefits. Current research has shown healthcare professionals play a paramount role in the acceptance of in silico technologies, as they form the bridge between the developers of the technologies and the broader public¹⁶. To engage with HCPs, we have developed series of information packages specifically for healthcare professionals, who are new or less familiar with in silico medicine. The specific information package presented henceforth is tailored for healthcare professionals, whereby the ISW project outcomes as well as generic material from the wider in silico community are carefully curated. Collectively, packages 1 to 3 of this chapter are aimed at not only introducing HCPs to in silico technologies, but also offer materials to increase their awareness, understanding and engagement with the field of in silico medicine and the in silico trial technologies.

2.1 *Package1: General introduction to ‘what is in silico medicine’*

Learning and information materials introduce a domain to a non-technical audience, including healthcare professionals. They offer self-reading content in the form of brochures, booklets, videos and play a crucial role to build familiarity of the in silico medicine. More importantly, they explain its potential to non-technical healthcare experts, like students in medical school, as well as healthcare experts undergoing continuous medical education, within their professional environment like hospitals, regulatory agencies, health technology assessment bodies as well as governmental organisations like national competent authorities.

The following three subsections present introductory topics in layperson language, factoring non-technical audience. This may appeal to healthcare professionals, as a beginner’s read on in silico medicine domain.

¹⁶ Winter, P., & Carusi, A. (2022). ‘If You’re Going to Trust the Machine, Then That Trust Has Got to Be Based on Something’: : Validation and the Co-Constitution of Trust in Developing Artificial Intelligence (AI) for the Early Diagnosis of Pulmonary Hypertension (PH) . *Science & Technology Studies*, 35(4), 58–77. <https://doi.org/10.23987/sts.102198>.

2.1.1 Unravelling the science

Introduction to in silico medicine – for beginners

The following section presents a high-level introduction to the domain of in silico medicine, whereby the science behind the technology is unravelled for non-domain experts, including those healthcare professionals, who are new to the field of in silico medicine.

Introduction to the science around in silico medicine

Digital and technological innovations profoundly impact biomedical research and clinical practice, allowing for a whole new way to deal with healthcare. The research and the clinical community commonly refer to this new approach as *in silico* medicine or the use of computer modelling and simulation in all areas of healthcare. The term *in silico* refers to silicon, the main component of computer chips. It relates to other standard biological science methods, such as *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

At the heart of *in silico* medicine lies the concept of Computer Modelling and Simulation (CM&S). This powerful tool harnesses the laws of mathematics, physics, and chemistry to develop a model, or a “virtual twin”, of an organ, a system, a human being, or even a population.

Computer modelling and simulation have a rich history of successful applications across various fields, particularly in engineering. Its versatility is evident in the computer simulation of the behaviour of buildings and bridges in different use and weather conditions, the aerodynamic simulation of aeroplanes and F1 cars, and the development of flight simulators for pilot training and navigation systems. These achievements serve as a testament to the power and potential of this technology, inspiring the exploration of innovative healthcare applications.

In healthcare, such technology has already been applied, for instance, to create a virtual twin of different organs and systems, such as the heart. The virtual heart twin replicates the morphology and physiology of a patient-specific heart, allowing clinicians and surgeons to investigate the patient’s condition better and test the results of a specific surgical procedure or the application of a particular medical device.

Types of modelling – for beginners

To alleviate the definitional challenges among the HCPs, a brief summary of type of modelling approaches is summarized. Starting from *what is a model?* And moving towards the spectrum of *knowledge driven to data-driven modelling paradigms*, the technologies behind in silico medicine are introduced to the non-technical reader, with help of real-world examples like the design of racing cars and weather predictions.

Models

An *in silico* model is, in other words, the mathematical description of how something works, and such a model can be used to simulate its behaviour. Many things can be modelled and simulated, including objects, weather forecasts and even (parts of) the human body. Different types of models can be employed for such applications, and they can be classified depending on how they are built.

Knowledge-based vs data-based models

The so-called **knowledge-based models** are based on the laws of physics, chemistry, or mathematics to describe, for instance, the heart's beating or how an electrochemical signal is transmitted through the brain and the nerves.

However, it is also possible to describe something only using data, without having to be based only on the laws governing such system or process. This is possible thanks to the ability of computers to process and make sense of enormous amounts of data. Those are called **data-driven models** and include technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL). These data-driven models can “learn” from large datasets and provide answers to specific questions. For instance, such tools can be employed to recognise specific features, such as early signs of tumours in medical images and alert the medical personnel whenever needed.

Such a distinction between **knowledge-based** and **data-driven models** is, in most real-life applications weaker, since both approaches are necessary to answer clinical questions and best be blended into an hybrid model.

Role of computer models in healthcare

The application of computer models in healthcare may provide a long list of benefits, especially to improve the efficiency of different processes. **A computer program, for instance, can scan medical images nonstop and report only those that need a second check by doctors.** Moreover, this approach would **reduce the variability due to human observers.** **Further they also reduce the workload for clinicians,** allowing more time for an improved and collaborative interaction with their patients.

Clinical vs In silico Clinical Trials – for beginners

HCPs play a crucial role of being gatekeepers within the regulatory and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) phases, where they evaluate the clinical effectiveness of new medical products through (randomized) clinical trials, as well as through assessing real-world evidence. As in silico technologies are slated to make a paradigm shift through augmenting the conventional clinical trials, it becomes important that HCPs are best informed on in silico clinical trials.

Clinical vs in silico clinical trials

Before you can benefit from a drug or a medical device, they have to go through a lengthy journey as they must be evaluated in pre-clinical and clinical trials to ensure their effectiveness and safety.

These trials take years to complete, cost millions, and less than one out of ten drugs entering clinical trials reaches the market. However, thanks to computer models, it is possible to streamline this process.

Computer-simulated trials, or in silico trials, hold significant promise. They offer a range of benefits, including a substantial reduction in animal and human testing. This is possible through the use of virtual populations, which are computer models, based on real patients.

Such virtual populations help test large and diverse groups over a long period, ensuring the inclusion of underrepresented groups, such as children. Running an in silico trial before a traditional trial can also help reduce the risks and increase the safety of human testing.

In silico trials are faster and cheaper than traditional clinical trials, boosting innovation and benefiting early access for patients. This requires a strong collaboration among scientists, healthcare professionals, patients and many more actors striving to realise their full potential.

Further reading on unravelling the science

For an extended reading on the topic of 'Unravelling the science behind in-silico medicine', we refer you to the 'Chapter 6 of the In silico Medicine Info kit – Resource A'¹⁷.

¹⁷ M. Contin et al (2024). An in silico medicine Info kit for effective stakeholder engagement. www.vph-institute.org - September 2024 at VPH 2024.

2.1.2 [Multimedia resource](#)

Multimedia content are critical resources to address the challenges associated with familiarity about *in silico* technologies. They contribute towards informing and educating the wider public, patients or patient organisations, as well as healthcare professionals, regarding the scope and potential of *in silico* medicine. Such informational materials are fundamental to introducing an evolving domain. The Virtual Physiological Human Institutes (VPHi), a member of the ISW consortium, is constantly involved in producing this type of communication material to be used at specific events, for specific projects and/or to be made available on our channels or through targeted communications.

Introductory videos – for beginners

As part of ISW information packages, **VPHi**, is producing a series of **animated videos – “Code & Cure”** that span from a general introduction of *in silico* medicine to all the way up to full-length clinical applications of *in silico* technologies. These cover the different types of computer models, *in silico* trials, and social and ethical impacts of the technologies.

It is important to note that these introductory videos targeting the layman audience, is of relevance to HCPs on following counts:

- Early stage HCPs and allied HCPs, i.e. students, may find simple video animations to quickly grasp, before exploring in-depth self-reading material.
- Experienced HCPs may find these introductory videos as icebreakers, to engage with fellow professional colleagues, who are new to the domain.
- For all HCP groups, including those within the healthcare, regulatory, HTA's and policy making agencies, who may often need to engage and explain *in silico* technologies to their own stakeholders, be it patients, general public or politicians, these animated videos could lower the barrier of engagement

Code & Cure: Introduction to In Silico medicine

A series of 8 small videos, consciously kept sharp and short (less than 90 seconds), is released as a video library throughout 2024, under this playlist:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLo-UtC9aT9rvmgBZAienlaGpBTHrWXfx>

Introductory videos – “Code & Cure”		
CODE & CURE	DESCRIPTION	COVER
EPISODE 1 UNDERSTANDING IN SILICO MEDICINE 1 min 26 sec	What is the next big thing in healthcare? In silico medicine, of course. But what is it? Let’s discover it together with the series “Code & Cure: Understanding In Silico Medicine”. This first video explains in a very simple way the concept of in silico medicine and what it can do for all of us. LINK: https://youtu.be/5YjjzHHsok	
EPISODE 2 WHAT IS A COMPUTER MODEL? 1 min 27 sec	You might not notice it, but computer models are everywhere around us, from your smartphone calculating the fastest route to work to the aerodynamic simulations of cars and planes. In this video, we will discover how we can make the most of them for a better healthcare. LINK: https://youtu.be/gAeHWcKxDZl	
EPISODE 3 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEALTHCARE 1 min 7 sec	As an in silico medicine tool, Artificial Intelligence plays an important role in many aspects of medical clinics. In this video, we will show how, thanks to AI, we can turn all the data surrounding us into actionable medical decisions. LINK: https://youtu.be/xctWc8n7eC8	
EPISODE 4 TECHNOLOGIES BEHIND IN SILICO MEDICINE	In silico medicine wouldn't be possible without many supporting technologies. The fourth video of the series Code & Cure will present how medical imaging, supercomputers, and virtual and augmented reality (AR/VR) contribute to it. LINK: https://youtu.be/igDpowgVSgA	
EPISODE 5-8	In-progress	In-progress

Short podcasts – for beginners & professionals

Podcasts are a powerful tool to convey complex topics to broader audiences. Differently from radio, podcasts are thematic and on-demand. The listeners can decide the topic they want to listen, and listen to it wherever and whenever they prefer. For instance, combining it with their drive home or a run.

Healthcare professionals are often overstretched with their clinical, administrative and personal time, while striving to inform themselves on the latest healthcare advancements. Leveraging the unique characteristics of the podcast medium, we have developed a series of *in silico*-centric introductory podcasts between 10 and 30 minutes in length, which could be their average home-to-work commute.

The VPHi team is producing a podcast dedicated to *in silico* medicine called **The Digital Twin Theory**. This podcast aims at informing and involving a lay audience of science enthusiasts and patients interested *in silico* medicine. Each episode includes a simple discussion about an *in silico* medicine topic with an expert. The experts being interviewed are young scientists, experienced professors, doctors, policymakers, social scientists, philosophers, and more.

Introductory podcasts – “The Digital Twin Theory”		
THE DIGITAL TWIN THEORY	DESCRIPTION	COVER
EPISODE 1 INTRODUCTION TO SILICO MEDICINE 12 min 09 sec	<p>In silico medicine is the future of healthcare, but is it really? And what can it do for us? We interviewed Liesbet Geris, professor of Biomechanics and Computational Tissue Engineering at the University of Liege and KU Leuven. She’s also the executive director of the Virtual Physiological Human Institute.</p> <p>Youtube Spotify</p>	
EPISODE 2 HOW MODELS WORK? 12 min 39 sec	<p>What is a computer model? How can we build one? How can they be used to improve healthcare? We asked all such questions to Himanshu Kaul, Royal Academy of Engineering Research Fellow and Principal Investigator at the Laboratory for Multiscale Emergent Bioengineering at the University of Leicester</p> <p>Youtube</p>	
EPISODE 3 THE POWER OF AI IN MEDICINE 13 min 59 sec	<p>As an in silico medicine tool, Artificial Intelligence is revolutionising healthcare. When did it start? And how can AI contribute to improving and making doctors’ work more efficient worldwide? We asked such questions to Leonardo Castorina, PhD student in Biomedical AI at the University of Edinburgh, specialising in AI-driven protein design and immune system research.</p> <p>Youtube</p>	
EPISODE 4 VIRTUAL PATIENTS	<p>Drug development, testing, and approval take 10 to 15 years and cost millions of euros. Most of this time and money go into clinical trials, which are essential for proving the drug’s safety and effectiveness.</p> <p>Clinical trials are crucial, but can we make this process faster, cheaper, and safer for both animals and humans? The short answer is yes. For the longer answer, we turn to the guest of this episode, Francesco Pappalardo, Professor of Computer Science at the University of Catania.</p> <p>Spotify</p>	
EPISODE 5	In-progress	

2.2 Package 2: Glossaries & position papers

2.2.1 Glossaries with terminologies of in silico technologies

Glossaries are lists of terminologies designed to educate the community, fostering clarity and addressing definitional challenges, thereby enhancing awareness and understanding among stakeholders.

Within the in silico medicine context, there are occasional confusions and diverging opinions on certain terminology which may lead to misunderstanding regarding the meaning of some *in silico* medicine concepts used in the literature. Having a common vocabulary is the basis for all engagement activities.

The following are few key terminologies frequently referenced within the in silico world project.

Glossary of key in silico terminologies

Computer Modelling and Simulation (CM&S): Computer modelling and simulation refer to the process of using computer programs and mathematical algorithms to replicate real-world phenomena or systems. It involves creating digital representations of physical objects, processes, or situations to analyse and predict their behaviour.

In silico trials (IST): In silico trials are a type of simulation-based experimentation conducted entirely using CM&S. These trials replicate various aspects of real clinical trials, drug testing, or product evaluations by using computer models and data to simulate the effects and outcomes, providing insights into safety, efficacy, and other critical factors.

In silico medicine (ISM): In silico medicine is a field of medical research and practice that leverages CM&S to advance understanding, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases. It encompasses the use of computational tools to analyse biological data, simulate physiological processes, and develop personalized treatment strategies, ultimately contributing to more effective and personalized healthcare solutions.

The members of the ISW project are actively involved in shaping glossaries of in silico technologies, which are further detailed in the following sub-sections.

Glossary in scientific literature – for beginners

HCPs use scientific literature to keep them informed of the evolving technologies but also to draw impression on what it takes to transform such evolutions into clinical practice. As professionals, they seek scientific publications and reports on (randomized) clinical trial outcomes and real-world evidence.

To provide both the modelling community and HCPs with a clarity on definitions in scientific publications, a team of members from the academia (VPHi) including those consortium members of ISW project and the industry ([Avicenna Alliance](#)), regularly collate a list of words and *in silico* related terminologies. Through consensus, the meaning of commonly used terms is clarified, for use in publications. The [Avicenna Alliance](#) produced a third release (August 2023) of its living glossary of computational modelling and simulation terms. The glossary is a ready to use in silico dictionary for both beginners and professionals among HCPs, who are new to the domain.

Avicenna Alliance Glossary on CM&S¹⁸

(A short list of key terminologist from Avicenna Alliance Glossary¹⁸)

General

Digital Evidence (i.e., *in silico* evidence)

Results of computational modelling and simulation submitted as part of a (regulatory) evaluation process provided in a prescribed format that encompasses *in silico* trials and *in silico* tests.

Digital twin

A computational model of physical assets (or processes or systems) that learns and is updated from multiple sources, in real-time or not, depending on the context of use. It acts as a bridge between the physical and virtual world, allowing analysis (e.g. simulations) that can help anticipate problems and plan for the future.

Virtual patient

A virtual patient can be considered as a computational model and simulation that represents the peculiar characteristics of one human subject (e.g., anatomy, (patho) physiology and/or lifestyle) and his/her interaction with the medicinal product of interest; and predicts (as opposed to measuring experimentally) quantities of interest necessary to support decision-making within a specific context of use.

Context of Use (CoU)

Defines the specific role and scope of the computational model used to address the question of interest. It should include a detailed statement of what will be modelled and how the outputs from the computational model will be used to answer or inform the question of interest. It is important to note that the CoU is distinct from the “indications for use” or “intended use” of a medical device, which are descriptions of how a device is intended to be used in clinical practice¹⁹.

Process definitions

Adequacy assessment

Process of evaluating the evidence in support of credibility of a computational model, for a given context of use, and making a determination on whether the evidence is sufficient.

Uncertainty Quantification (UQ)

Activity to determine how the uncertainty in the model inputs (e.g., parameters, initial conditions) propagates into uncertainty in the model outputs; it is the process of identifying,

¹⁸Avicenna Alliance Glossary: Version 3.0 (August 2023) - https://www.avicenna-alliance.com/upload/aa-glossary-of-terms-august-2023_650182e1ef38d.pdf.

¹⁹ Assessing Credibility of Computational Modeling through Verification and Validation: Application to Medical Devices V&V 40 – 2018. ASME, 2018. 60p. ISBN: 9780791872048.

characterising, and quantifying those factors that could affect the accuracy of computational results (based on FDA definitions in several guidance documents).

Applicability

Relevance of the credibility assessment of the computational model (e.g. verification and validation activities, uncertainty quantification) for a given context of use.

V&V 40 definitions**Credibility**

Represents the belief in the predictive capability of the computational model for the context of use (COU) applying engineering judgement based on the available evidence. (Reference: ASME V&V 40 – 2018¹⁹). See “Model credibility”.

Model credibility

Refers to the trust in the predictive capability of the computational modelling and simulation for the COU. Trust can be established through the collection of verification and validation (V&V) evidence and by demonstrating the applicability of the V&V activities to support the use of the computational model for the COU¹⁹.

Uncertainty

Potential deficiencies in any phase or activity of modelling, computation, or experimentation process that is due to inherent stochasticity (aka aleatoric uncertainty), lack of knowledge or unreliable knowledge (aka epistemic uncertainty)¹⁹.

Verification

A computational model is the numerical implementation of an underlying mathematical model. The objective of verification is to ensure that the mathematical model is implemented correctly and then accurately solved¹⁹.

Validation

Activity demonstrating that the underlying mathematical model correctly represents the reality of interest within the Context of Use. The process of determining the degree to which a model or a simulation is an accurate representation of the real world¹⁹.

Glossary in position papers – for beginners & professionals

Glossaries are also an essential part of position/white papers advocating for *in silico* medicine. Such advocacy initiatives are primarily targeted towards interdisciplinary audiences like technology developers and HCPs. Glossaries can help acknowledge the difference in definitions or the presence of multiple definitions, subject to the community that uses it. They also help clarify the difference in the way the technology is used.

For the attention of HCPs, the following table presents a shortlist of terminologies from the white paper on “The Role of Artificial Intelligence within *in Silico Medicine*”²⁰. It summarises a non-exhaustive lexicon of terminologies on all terms related to *in silico* technologies, including several definitions for certain terms, whose definitions differ subject to the community and the context in which it is used. The intention is not to duplicate or limit to key terminologies, but rather introduce this piece of ready-to-use information for the healthcare professional community, who are often hammered by technical jargon from interdisciplinary experts.

²⁰ Avicenna Alliance [white paper on “The Role of Artificial Intelligence within *In Silico Medicine*”](#).

Definition of in silico terminologies differ based on community & context²¹

Knowledge-driven models (used as synonyms: mechanistic models, hypothesis-based models, physics-based models or white box models):

in silico models that are based on prior knowledge on cause-and-effect relationships^{22,23}.

Data-driven models (used as synonyms: phenomenological models, empirical models, black box models):

in silico models that develop a predictor automatically for the data without making any causal assumptions are called data-driven models. In this context, models utilizing statistics, artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning are considered data-driven models.

Machine Learning (ML): ML is the scientific study of computer algorithms that are able to learn and adapt through experience. ML algorithms build a model based on training data, in order to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed to do so²⁴. There are three main categories of ML algorithms: supervised, unsupervised and reinforced. Within (and across) these categories, different ML models have been developed such as artificial neural networks (which also make up the backbone of the ML subgroup called deep learning²⁵), evolutionary algorithms, etc.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): There is a large variety in definitions of AI. We refer the reader to the 2021 Joint Research Centre (JRC) report²⁴ providing a full taxonomy of AI. Here we cite several definitions currently used by the European Commission and other international organisations. The common element is the ability to learn from data and adapt its behaviour accordingly.

- European Union (EU) high-level expert group on AI²⁶: AI refers to systems that display intelligent behaviour by analysing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals. In the context of this paper, only the purely software-based AI systems are considered (and more specifically, the analytical AI that is focused on cognitive intelligence and decision-making as opposed to human-inspired or humanised AI). Hardware-based AI systems that are also included in this definition are beyond the scope of this paper.

²¹ Avicenna Alliance [white paper on “The Role of Artificial Intelligence within *In Silico* Medicine](#)

²² Transtrum M.K. & Qiu P. (2016). Bridging Mechanistic and Phenomenological Models of Complex Biological Systems. *PLoS Comput Biol.* 12(5):e1004915. doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004915.

²³ Lema-Perez L. (2019). On parameter interpretability of phenomenological-based semiphysical models in biology. *Inform. Med. Unlocked* 15, 100158. doi:ff10.1016/j.imu.2019.02.002f

²⁴ Samoili, S., et al. (2021), AI Watch. Defining Artificial Intelligence 2.0, EUR 30873 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, ISBN 978-92-76-42648-6, doi:10.2760/019901, JRC126426

²⁵ Ching, T., D. S. et al. (2018). “Opportunities and obstacles for deep learning in biology and medicine.” *J R Soc Interface* 15(141). doi: 10.1098/rsif.2017.0387

²⁶<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/definition-artificial-intelligence-main-capabilities-and-scientific-disciplines>

- AI Act (European Commission (EC), 2021)²⁷: AI system means software that is developed with one or more of the techniques and approaches mentioned hereafter and can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with. The aforementioned techniques and approaches are:
 - Machine learning approaches, including supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement learning, using a wide variety of methods including deep learning;
 - Logic- and knowledge-based approaches, including knowledge representation, inductive (logic) programming, knowledge bases, inference and deductive engines, (symbolic) reasoning and expert systems;
 - Statistical approaches, Bayesian estimation, search and optimization methods.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)²⁸. An AI system is a machine based system that is capable of influencing the environment by producing an output (predictions, recommendations or decisions) for a given set of objectives. It uses machine and/or human-based data and inputs to:
 - Perceive real and/or virtual environments;
 - Abstract these perceptions into models through analysis in an automated manner (*e.g.*, with machine learning), or manually; and
 - Use model inference to formulate options for outcomes.

AI systems are designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy.

Digital Twin: definitions vary among the use of digital twins in engineering or healthcare contexts.

- In engineering, a digital twin is defined as a set of virtual information constructs that mimic the structure, context, and behaviour of an individual/unique physical asset, process or entity, is dynamically updated with data from its physical twin throughout the period where the twin is used to support decisions, and ultimately informs decisions that realize value.
- In healthcare the term is often used in the context of personalised medicine, as the direct use of individual specific models for the prevention, prediction, screening, diagnosis and treatment of a disease, as well as the evaluation, optimization, selection and personalisation of intervention options²⁹.

To acknowledge this is a relaxed version of the original definition of a digital twin, it will be called a digital patient, a virtual patient, a virtual twin, a digital avatar, a human digital twin or a digital twin for personalised medicine.

Further reading

For an extensive read on the glossary of in silico technology related terminologies, we strongly advocate the reference to the following publications:

1. Avicenna Alliance Glossary: Version 3.0 (August 2023) - https://www.avicenna-alliance.com/upload/aa-glossary-of-terms-august-2023_650182e1ef38d.pdf
2. Avicenna Alliance [white paper on “The Role of Artificial Intelligence within *In Silico* Medicine](#)

²⁷ European Commission, Communication 2021/0106 (COD): Proposal for a regulation of the european parliament and of the council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts.

²⁸ OECD Framework for the Classification of AI systems, OECD Digital Economy Papers, No. 323, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/cb6d9eca-en>.

²⁹ Consensus definition from the European Commission workshop on the human digital twin December 2020.

2.2.2 [Position papers & review articles](#)

Position papers are short publications that present the problem, the current state and a convincing solution related to a certain challenge. White papers on the potential of computer modelling and simulation in healthcare, aim to stimulate policy making, regulatory thinking and research strategies, establishing a perspective for the *in silico* domain, as well as help clarify boundaries and overlaps with other interdisciplinary areas.

Introductory position papers – for beginners

VPHi as a member of ISW consortium, actively collaborates with the [Avicenna Alliance](#) on a number of advocacy activities. Together with ISW consortium members, numerous position papers have been released tackling key issues for the in silico medicine community. Listing the exhaustive library of position papers pertaining to the domain is outside the scope of this package. Instead, a short list of position papers on in silico trial technologies that are of immediate relevance to the healthcare professionals is curated for the quick read of beginners, who are in the journey of familiarizing themselves about the domain of in silico technologies.

Position papers about In silico medicine

A short list of key position papers from the community, outlining the evolution, potential, challenges and roadmaps on in silico medicine.

- 2023: Position paper on **“The potential of in silico approaches to streamline drug development”**
- 2022: White paper on **“The Role of Artificial Intelligence within In Silico Medicine”**
- 2022: Position paper on **“Toward a Regulatory Pathway for Using In Silico Trials in CE Marking Position Paper”**

Digital twins in health care

- 2023: Viceconti M, De Vos M, Mellone S, Geris L. **Position paper From the digital twins in healthcare to the Virtual Human Twin: a moon-shot project for digital health research.** IEEE J Biomed Health Inform. 2023 Oct 11;PP. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2023.3323688. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 37819828.

Roadmap on In silico Clinical Trials

- **2016: Avicenna Alliance Roadmap:** Viceconti, Marco & Henney, Adriano & Morley-Fletcher, Edwin. (2016). **in silico Clinical Trials: How Computer Simulation will Transform the Biomedical Industry.** <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2756.6164>.

Review papers – for beginners and professionals

This sub-section summarises a couple of review papers that ponder over the use of the in silico trial technologies, in the context of regulatory evaluation of medical and medicinal products. This is a key area that the ISW consortium has been historically championing and proactively leading community efforts. In the interest of **HCPs, who are at the forefront of evaluating regulatory evidence** from in silico technologies, the following non-exhaustive list would be a good start to familiarize on the use of in silico solutions for regulatory approval.

Key publications around in silico trials

A short list of peer-reviewed publications from the in silico community, outlining the **in silico trial technologies for use in regulatory evidence generation**.

In silico trials

- 2024: **Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best practices for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products**. In: Synthesis Lectures on Biomedical Engineering. Viceconti M. & Emili L. (Eds.), Springer Cham eBook. ISBN: 978-3-031-48283-0, 2024.
- 2021: Viceconti M, Emili L, Afshari P, Courcelles E, Curreli C, Famaey N, Geris L, Horner M, Jori MC, Kulesza A, Loewe A, Neidlin M, Reiterer M, Rousseau CF, Russo G, Sonntag SJ, Voisin EM, Pappalardo F. **Possible Contexts of Use for in silico trials Methodologies: A Consensus-Based Review**. IEEE J Biomed Health Inform. 2021 Oct;25(10):3977-3982. doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2021.3090469. Epub 2021 Oct 5. PMID: 34161248.
- 2021: M. Viceconti, F. Pappalardo, B. Rodriguez, M. Horner, J. Bischoff, and F. M. Tshinanu, **“In silico trials: Verification, validation and uncertainty quantification of predictive models used in the regulatory evaluation of biomedical products,”** Methods, vol. 185, pp. 120–127, 2021.

Regulatory reports from ISW consortium

- Viceconti, M., Pappalardo, F., Curreli, C., Russo, G., & Aldieri, A. (2024). Regulatory Barriers to the adoption of in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948478>
- Viceconti, M., Curreli, C., Aldieri, A., & Pappalardo, F. (2024). BBCT-Hip Qualification advice with EMA - Public Domain Documents (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10938447>
- Pappalardo, F., Viceconti, M., Curreli, C., & Russo, G. (2024). UISS-TB Qualification advice with EMA - Public Domain Documents (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10939450>

2.3 Package 3: Scenarios, case studies & success stories

Through fictive clinical scenarios, case studies and success stories of in silico technologies, the communication and engagement between modelers and HCPs can be improved. These provide tangible examples of technological advancements, where the context is set through real-world clinical needs. HCPs often seek such structured examples to understand the value of health technologies, where the **innovations address unmet clinical needs**.

This information package presents **three representative fictive scenarios, three real-world case studies from the ISW consortium and one success story from community**. The descriptions start from an unmet clinical need, before moving into in silico context and finally ending with a brief note on the clinical application of the proposed technology.

2.3.1 In silico scenarios - for beginners and professionals

Open-ended real-world clinical scenarios facilitate discussions about the technical feasibility, clinical effectiveness, and also critical ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) of in silico medicine. VPHi has experimented with the use of such scenarios as fictive examples amongst diverse healthcare stakeholders, including patients, clinicians, patient advocates and healthcare legal teams, to unearth their opinions and concerns around the adoption of in silico medicine³⁰. Though fictive, they set the **context for structuring the conversations among stakeholders**, who are often not familiar with clinical or technical terminologies.

The following subsections present a series of six example scenarios, questioning the predictive (and thus preventive) ability of computer modelling and simulation techniques. These scenarios are helpful to steer open discussions amongst the HCPs and their stakeholders, to unearth the needs, reservations, barriers and more importantly social implications. These can serve as **education material for beginners**, as well as **discussion tools amongst the professional HCP peer-group**, to openly introspect the strengths and weaknesses around in silico technologies.

³⁰ Elhadj, Van Horenbeeck, Lievevrouw, and Van Hoyweghen. Rep. *WP5 Stakeholder Engagement - Focus Groups Analysis*, 2023. Available on ISW SharePoint.

Scenario 1: In silico paediatric clinical trial

“SimR4Child” scenario depicts the application of in silico trial for clinical trials involving paediatric groups.

In silico paediatric clinical trial

Clinical trials are necessary to prove that new treatments work well and are safe, but each patient is different and results in adults cannot be easily translated to children so dedicated trials are necessary. Nevertheless, trials involving children pose technical and ethical questions. In this scenario, the SimR4Child research group, in Germany, wants to treat a disease affecting the respiratory and digestive systems in children. Of course, we are all different but we also sometimes share characteristics with others. Thus, some children can share traits that may make them more or less responsive to the tested treatment. To limit the number of participants and avoid unnecessary tests, the SimR4Child group must find the most relevant target population for the treatment and select trial participants accordingly. To do that the researchers create a virtual population of patients in the computer, based on rules describing the behaviour of their respiratory and digestive systems and representing the variation in the real patient population (e.g. in terms of length). With that virtual population and thanks to mathematical calculation, they predict the physiological traits that characterize the best-responders and recommend these criteria for the recruitment in the real trial. The treatment will only be evaluated for this restricted population.

Scenario 2: Cardiovascular: For faster and safer device testing

“VirHeart” scenario presents faster and safer testing of heart valves using in silico testing methods.

Virtual testing of prosthetic valve

VirtHeart is a medical device company developing cardiac medical devices. They want to know the risk of leaks with their new prosthetic valve according to the physiological geometry of patients' hearts. The company generates a library of possible geometries based on medical imaging data. The geometries are reconstructed in 3D in the computer; they also create a numerical replica of the prosthetic valve that shares common physical properties and shape. With that they can simulate different scenarios without any animal or human experimentation, and identify typical geometries or physiological traits associated with a higher risk or lower risk of a leak. VirtHeart wants to use that numerical evidence to justify and support the requested medical indication (i.e. target population) in the regulatory dossier for marketing authorization.

Scenario 3 : Health prediction and preventive intervention

“HospiPlus” scenario presents medicinal treatment for John vs surgical intervention for Jenny.

Health prediction and preventive intervention

The new HospiPlus hospital of London allows medical doctors to “read” Jenny and John’s DNA with bio-informatics tools. An artificial intelligence algorithm predicts that Jenny has a high risk of developing osteoarthritis, a degenerative disease of the knee joint. With the same tool, the medical doctors anticipate that John will develop type-I diabetes. Therefore, the doctors of HospiPlus anticipate the need for preventive surgery for Jenny and therapeutic treatment and close monitoring for John.

Scenario 4: Genetics / Musculoskeletal - For treatment prediction

“SimPharmaCop” scenario presents genetics based medicinal treatment prediction.

The researchers at SimPharmaCop, a pharmaceutical company, are looking for small chemical molecules (“drugs”) which can interfere with a protein (“target”) known to be responsible for a degenerative disease (so by targeting this protein with the small molecules, we could prevent the degenerative disease). The researchers develop a computational model of the target protein at the molecular level; in other words, they model the molecular structure of this protein. In parallel, they can also model the molecular structure of the drugs. Using computational methods, the structure of these small molecules (drugs) can be optimized so that it adequately binds and interacts with the target protein. Only the molecules with the best matches are retained for further optimization and experimental testing (in vitro and in vivo); the rest are discarded.

Scenario 5: Musculoskeletal - Personalised treatment - Virtual screening for hip replacement

“Future Orthopaedics” scenario present design of personalized treatment based on virtual screening for hip replacement.

Virtual population screening for hip replacement

Future Orthopedics is a company which has developed a new hip prosthesis that will be evaluated during a clinical trial. They plan to involve less patients than usual in this clinical trial because a virtual trial will also be conducted using virtual patients and computer models of the hip and of the new implant. The results of both the human and virtual trials will be compared. If the computer model is validated (this means that it shows good performance when compared to the results in humans), the results from both the human and the virtual trials will be considered. In case the computer model is not validated, it is abandoned for this trial and only the results from a regular clinical trial (but then with more patients) will be taken into account to make decisions.

Scenario 6 Cardiovascular Surgical planning - Computer-assisted surgery

“Brussels University Hospital” scenario shows planning computer assisted surgery, for cardiovascular application

Computer-assisted surgery

At the Brussels University Hospital, the cardiac surgeons use in silico models to plan surgeries before the actual intervention. With these in silico models, they obtain a virtual (computational) reconstruction of the patients’ heart and they can use patient-specific data to determine, for example, the best stent shape to use or the best positioning for this stent (tube to hold your arteries or veins open). This means that key decisions about the medical interventions are taken based on information obtained from the in silico models.

2.3.2 Case studies - for beginners and professionals

The following sub-section, presents three case studies where in silico solutions are proposed

1. To assess bone strength in an orthopaedic application
2. To evaluate new vaccines under development in Tuberculosis
3. To predict subject-specific corrective in-soles in musculoskeletal ailments

During the project, these in silico solutions have advanced through technology readiness levels. ISW project had gone the extra mile beyond the technical validity, by subjecting the solutions to the rigour of regulatory and clinical assessment.

Case study 1 : Predicting bone strength

Case study 1: Bone Strength

Clinical need / challenge

Investigate the efficacy of antiresorptive drugs, a class of drugs aimed at treating osteoporosis and preventing fragility bone fractures.

- Product Type: Drug
- Category: Musculoskeletal/orthopaedics
- Disease: Osteoporosis/ bone fracture

In silico method

At the core of *BoneStrength*, there is Biomechanical Computed Tomography (BCT), a Digital Twin pipeline that allows patient-specific femur fracture risk estimation starting from a femur CT scan and a few other personal data (such as height and weight).

In silico trial solution

Simulate a phase III clinical trial by creating a large number of virtual patients (~1000), estimating their bone ageing with and without pharmacological treatments over several years, and evaluating patient fracture risk in different scenarios.

Current state: regulatory evidence

- Viceconti, M., Curreli, C., Aldieri, A., & Pappalardo, F. (2024). BBCT-Hip Qualification advice with EMA - Public Domain Documents (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10938447>
- Clinical Validation of BBCT-hip (ValidaBBCT-hip) - <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT06270758?tab=table#trial-description>

Further reading

- Aldieri, A., Curreli, C., Szyszko, J. A., La Mattina, A. A. & Viceconti, M. Credibility assessment of computational models according to ASME V&V40: Application to the Bologna biomechanical computed tomography solution. *Comput. Methods Programs Biomed.* 240, 107727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2023.107727> (2023).
- Aldieri, A., Terzini, M., Audenino, A.L. *et al.* Personalised 3D Assessment of Trochanteric Soft Tissues Improves HIP Fracture Classification Accuracy. *Ann Biomed Eng* **50**, 303–313 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10439-022-02924-1>

Case study 2 : Modelling for vaccine development

Case study 2: Tuberculosis

Clinical need / challenge

Predict the outcome of new vaccination strategies for active tuberculosis.

- Product Type: Drug
- Category: Vaccine/infectious disease
- Disease: Tuberculosis, vaccine

In silico method

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis (*UISS-TB*) is a simulator of the immune system dynamics, particularly tailored to predict the response of the human immune system to exposure to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

In silico trial solution

In silico lab solution to predict the outcome of new vaccination strategies. Validated with data coming from clinical trials of two vaccines (RUTI and ID93+GLA-SE).

Current state: regulatory evidence

Positive regulatory submission of EMA qualification advice, based on validation using anonymized data coming from patients enrolled in the *STriTuVaD* EC-funded project.

- Pappalardo, F., Viceconti, M., Curreli, C., & Russo, G. (2024). *UISS-TB* Qualification advice with EMA - Public Domain Documents (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10939450>
- Pappalardo, F., Russo, G., Di Salvatore, V., Battiato, S., Guarnera, F., & Rondinella, A. (2024). *MSValid* Data Collection [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10875606>

Further reading

- Maleki A, Crispino E, Italia SA, Di Salvatore V, Chiacchio MA, Sips F, Bursi R, Russo G, Maimone D, Pappalardo F. (2023). Moving forward through the in silico modeling of multiple sclerosis: Treatment layer implementation and validation. *Comput Struct Biotechnol J*. 21:3081-3090. doi: 10.1016/j.csbj.2023.05.020. PMID: 37266405; PMCID: PMC10230825.

Case study 3 : Subject-specific in soles

Case study 3: In Sole

Clinical need / challenge

Corrective insoles are used worldwide to treat different foot pathologies, guide movement during daily life and sports or improve comfort. While many options of orthopaedic insoles exist, they are often not customized for the individual patient.

- Product Type: Medical Device
- Category: Musculoskeletal/orthopaedics
- Disease: plantar pressure/corrective insole/ orthopaedic/ podiatry

In silico method

InSole aims at combining subject-specific musculoskeletal models with novel predictive simulations for the personalized prescription of 3D-printed corrective shoe insoles. The integrated framework utilizes experimental measurements from a dedicated movement analysis dataset and plantar pressure to predict the optimal corrective stiffness and geometry of custom 3D-printed insoles to correct dynamic foot deformities during locomotion.

In silico trial solution

By combining computer models with 3D printing, we can achieve improved personalization and superior performance. The framework consists of the following steps:

- Patient complaint/presentation
- Patient assessment (i.e., anatomy, movement pattern, and plantar pressure)
- Personalised computational model development
- Simulation of movement using measured data
- Insole optimization simulations (stiffness and geometry)
- Prescription of optimized insoles

The framework has been developed and validated in a healthy population and will be extended to a larger patient group and other dynamic foot pathologies.

Current state: regulatory and clinical access

KU Leuven provides the methodological development and validation, whereas Materialise Motion will be responsible for insole framework deployment as an online service, integration with their industrial manufacturing process.

Further reading

- Killen BA, Van Rossom S, Burg F, Vander Sloten J and Jonkers I. (2024) *In-silico* techniques to inform and improve the personalized prescription of shoe insoles. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 12:1351403. doi: 10.3389/fbioe.2024.1351403.

2.3.3 Success story - for beginners and professionals

Success stories are a powerful way to promote *in silico* medicine among clinicians, patients, and policymakers. The storytelling format catches the attention and easily sticks in the mind of the reader/listener. They can be employed to show the progress of *in silico* medicine, involve and inform stakeholders, foster discussions, and attract new collaborations.

Success story 1: In silico solution for regulatory evidence and approval

This section presents a well-known and community acknowledged *in silico* clinical trial that substituted a conventional clinical trial³¹.

VICTRE Trial – a success story for in silico trial

VICTRE (Virtual Clinical Trial for Regulatory Evaluation), a **In Silico Breast Imaging Pipeline**, demonstrated that *in silico* imaging clinical trials can be an alternative source of evidence for regulatory evaluation, which can be cheaper and faster than human trials³¹.

In the 2018 VICTRE study, realised by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and published in the Journal of the American Medical Association (Sharma et al.³¹), was presented a comparison between a classical trial and an *in silico* trial. The topic was the comparison of two imaging techniques for the diagnosis of breast-related pathologies.

A classical trial was realised with actual patients, followed by an *in silico* trial with virtual patients. The **classical trial** involved 400 women in seven clinical sites who received double exposure to radiation over four years, with the involvement of 31 radiologists. The **virtual trial**, instead, saw the participation of 2986 virtual patients with diverse characteristics and taking less than two years.

The study of Sharma et al., showed that the conventional and the *in silico* trial reached the same conclusions, with the latter being faster, risk-free, and taking about one-third of the resources needed for the classical trial.

Therefore, the increasing employment of virtual trials to assess imaging systems could significantly decrease the burden of bringing new and improved imaging systems to the market.

References

- Sharma D, Graff CG, Badal A, Zeng R, Sawant P, Sengupta A, Dahal E, Badano A (2019). Technical Note: In silico imaging tools from the VICTRE clinical trial. Med Phys.;46(9):3924-3928. doi: 10.1002/mp.13674. Epub 2019 Jul 17. PMID: 31228352.
- <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/science-and-research-medical-devices/victre-silico-breast-imaging-pipeline>

This concludes the four information packages destined for creating basic awareness on *in silico* technologies. The following chapters introduces the formal lecture materials, custom-prepared for health care professionals.

³¹ Sharma D, Graff CG, Badal A, Zeng R, Sawant P, Sengupta A, Dahal E, Badano A. (2019). Technical Note: In silico imaging tools from the VICTRE clinical trial. Med Phys. 46(9):3924-3928. doi: 10.1002/mp.13674. PMID: 31228352.

3 Lecture materials for HCP

Briefly, ISW consortium organized questionnaires and a consensus workshop³², to identify **the macro level and micro level learning goals for each of the in silico technology stakeholders**³³ (see Appendix 1). This resulted in the definition of **full-length coursework** (between 3 and 12 European Credit Transfer System (ECTS)) per stakeholder category (see **Appendix 2**). With the objective to generate early momentum and interest for in silico technology courses among the target audience, lighter mini-courses are initially formulated. They are meant to quickly and effectively introduce fundamental concepts and practical applications, while also helping to collect valuable feedback to assess the effectiveness of the teaching methods. These mini-courses are offered as part of an **e-learning platform (see Appendix 4)**, whereby a pre- and post- questionnaire is included to study the impact of the learnings on the participants' familiarity and knowledge on in silico technologies. Moreover, the participant fill in a short evaluation form after each module in order to compare the perceived key aspects with the defined learning goals.

Learning goals of HCPs – students vs professionals

As outlined in the introduction, HCPs may already be subject matter experts in their profession, who are currently employed in stakeholder organisations like hospitals, industry or regulatory agencies, or students undergoing formal education at academic institutions, to become future employees at these stakeholder organisations. Assessment of learning goals for both groups of HCP categories, resulted in nearly similar **macro level skills and competencies (for details see Appendix 1, Appendix 3)**, with overlap in the relevant ILO's for the training and retraining. This indicated that independent of whether the HCP is undergoing education to become a professional or they are already in a professional capacity (e.g. within technology assessment committee), the necessary foundational courses on in silico technologies are identical, at least for the pre-liminary mini-courses. Therefore, for this package, we limit to the overarching common learning goals as the starting point of lecture materials for HCPs.

³² Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380239>.

³³ Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400657>.

3.1 Package 4: Lecture materials for HCP

This package summarizes an overview of lecture material formulated for HCPs. The key learning goals identified for all sub-categories of HCPs is formulated into mini-course, containing three modules, for non-technical stakeholders, independent of whether the participant is a new entrant/student or an expert HCP. The baseline is that both are beginners for in silico technologies.

The package is organized as follows:

- Section 3.1.1: The practical considerations like enrolment, handbook to e-learning platform, the structure of the coursework are briefly described.
- Section 3.1.2 - 3.1.4: A high-level walk-through of the three main modules of the lecture materials for non-technical HCPs are presented.

Note: For the internal reference (e.g. ISW reviewers), **LECTURE MATERIALS pertaining to HCPs** can be **locally accessed at the [ISW SharePoint site](#)**³⁴:

3.1.1 Practical: enrolment, self-assessment

The learning materials pertaining to mini-courses are currently offered in a moderated self-learning online platform – **Toledo Ultra Community portal**. Access to the lecture materials, can be facilitated by reaching out to the ISW project communication team (info@insilico.world) or by directly contacting the responsible project partner – KU Leuven MECH:

- Lise Gheysen (lise.gheysen@kuleuven.be)

The platform includes:

- A **self-assign and self-assessment tool** to evaluate the participants' prior knowledge.
 - The self-assign tool allows the participants to self-assign themselves to a stakeholder group and training level (beginner or retraining).
 - The self-assessment tool helps one to identify their skill level and to refresh or refine their knowledge if needed.
- **Pre-evaluation questionnaire** to capture the baseline of participant's understanding of in silico medicine.
- **Overview of modules**
 - With objectives and learning goals.
- Learning materials
 - **Slides materials in PDF format.**
 - **Recording of the coursework**, with video and voice over.
 - **Transcription** of the instructor.
- **Post-evaluation questionnaire** to capture any discernible differences in the knowledge of participants.

Further details on the e-learning portal are summarized in Appendix 4. A step-by-step guide with illustration of the graphical user interface of the e-learning platform is explained.

³⁴ [ISW SharePoint site](#) - (Documents/WP1/Deliverables/WP5_SUBMITTED/ ISW_D5.6_LectureMaterial-Healthcareprofessionals-Nontech/Module).

3.1.2 Module 1: Introduction to in silico medicine

Instructor

Marco Viceconti, Alma Mater Studiorum, University of Bologna, Italy.

Objective

This course module introduces the participants to some of the general concepts of in silico medicine technologies and discusses the related opportunities and limitations.

Learning Goals

After attending the lecture on “Introduction to in silico medicine” participants should be able to: ...

Learning goals

- Understand the complexity of dealing with predictions about human health;
- Identify the origins of barriers against adoption of in silico technologies (complexity, redundancy, stochasticity, culture);
- Summarize first examples of Digital Twins and In Silico Trials developed;
- Assess the value of the In Silico Trials in the development of new medical products;
- Outline the 3R concept that led In Silico Trials;
- Illustrate how In silico technologies might be of help to ensure and extend the healthcare given how the world population is growing;
- Explain what the Virtual Human Twin will be.

Course material

Title: The crafts of scientific modelling: Introduction to in silico medicine

Duration: 1h33m.

Date of creation: 2024-01-12.

A short overview of key slides and the corresponding transcripts illustrate the lecture on 'Introduction to In silico medicine'.

(1) Investigate living organism: in vitro, in vivo and in silico

(3) To cure is to predict

If you think about it, doctors constantly make predictions in daily practice. Consider a doctor who is presented with a young patient showing some symptoms. The doctor goes back to the knowledge she has accumulated during her training and her profession, and also to the experience that she had with other young patients who showed symptoms similar to those of the current patient and when treated in a certain way, showed an improvement. Using previous knowledge and past observations, the doctor predicts the best course of action for that patient.

(2) Definition: In silico medicine

(4) Data-driven vs Mechanistic Knowledge

Data-driven vs Mechanistic Knowledge can appear in form of implicit knowledge contained into data or in form of explicit knowledge obtained through the scientific process (if it resisted repeated falsification attempts). This has generated two families of modelling methods. The first one is often referred to as artificial intelligence, and includes data-driven models. This is based on the idea of collecting a lot of data about a phenomenon from which to extract implicit knowledge that can be used to provide predictions for individual patients. On the other hand, we have mechanistic models, which are built using a little bit of data and a lot of mechanistic knowledge. This knowledge is used to build a predictive model in form of mathematical equations.

(5) Developing a new drug costs \$2.5 mil

Drugs today are developed by trial and error. This method works very well in bringing to the market only drugs that are safe and effective. But it costs too much, and these costs impact on the selling price of these new products. It also reduces the competition, as only big pharma can afford to invest such huge amounts to develop a new product.

(6) 3R: animal replacement & In silico trials

Some countries approved legislations about complete elimination of animal experimentation. The discussion on possible alternatives to animal experimentation, which poses ethical concerns, introduced the 3R concept: Refinement (reduce the suffering of the animal), Reduction (reduce of the number of animals), Replacement (elimination of animal experimentation). Similarly, In Silico Trials can be used to refine, reduce and replace in vitro experiments, animal experiments and human experiments.

3.1.3 Module 2: Experimental validation of predictive models

Instructor

Luca Cristofolini, Alma Mater Studiorum, University of Bologna, Italy.

Marco Viceconti, Alma Mater Studiorum, University of Bologna, Italy.

Objective

An in silico model can only be considered credible when it is properly validated with an experiment. The course module indicates how such a proper validation experiment can be developed and illustrates this with state-of-the-art examples. The seminar is dedicated to the credibility assessment of a predictive model.

Learning Goals

After attending the lecture on "Experimental validation of models". participants should be able to: ...

Learning goals

- Explain the difference between numeric, epistemic and aleatoric errors in in silico modeling;
- Identify the five requirements to develop a credible validation framework and apply those to a state-of-the-art research problem;
- Formulate the difference in characteristics of numerical models and in vitro experiments;
- Summarize two examples of in silico models and how they can be experimentally validated;
- Clarify the meaning of the modeling concepts registration, segmentation and meshing, together with their role in the validation process.

Course material

Title: Experimental validation of predictive models.

Duration: 1h42m & Date of creation: 2024-02-09.

A short overview of key slides and corresponding transcripts illustrate the lecture on 'Experimental validation of predictive models'.

The purposes of scientific models

- Models to test theories**
 - Models can be used to materialise theories and make operationally easier to explore if such theories are compatible with available experimental observation.
 - Comparison to experimental data aims to falsify the theory used to build the model
- Models to solve problems**
 - Models that are built with theories that have resisted extensive falsification efforts can be used to solve problems
 - Comparison to experimental data aims to quantify the predictive accuracy, assuming the theories used to build the model are valid

(6) The purposes of scientific models
 Models can be used to increase our knowledge, by testing or falsifying theories, or to solve problems, starting from knowledge already considered valid. In both cases, the credibility of the model has to be assessed. The term *credibility* refers to the ability of the model to predict the physical reality, and it can be evaluated comparing the predictions (of the model) to measurements taken through controlled experiments.

Credibility Analysis plan

- The predictive error of a model is the sum of three components

$$\alpha_m = \alpha_f + \varepsilon_f + v_{f,I}$$
 - Numeric:** due to approximations
 - Verification
 - Epistemic:** due to model assumptions
 - Validation
 - Aleatoric:** due to inputs
 - Uncertainty quantification

(2) Credibility Analysis plan
 Predictive error is made of three components (Numeric, Epistemic and Aleatoric). The seminar is focused on one of those: the Epistemic error, which is tightly linked to the modelling assumptions.

The heart of credibility: validation

- Design controlled experiments that represent as closely as possible the phenomenon you are modelling
- Ensure the experimental measurements are reliable (nearly null systematic error, high reproducibility)
- Develop a robust protocol to register the model to the experiment in space and time
- Develop an accurate idealisation of the boundary conditions and full characterisation of the constitutive equations
- Define a rigorous framework to compare predictions with experimental measurements

(3) Validation
 The heart of the credibility assessment is the validation step, which is performed through controlled experiments. These experiments need to be reliable, reproducible, with systematic and aleatoric errors as small as possible. The protocols need to be robust enough to allow for a correct registration of the model to the experiment. In addition, the model's boundary conditions, together with the constitutive equations, need to be accurately idealized. In the end, a rigorous way to compare the model's prediction and the (corresponding) experimental measure is required.

Reliability of models must be proven

Validation: process of determining if a model of a physical event represents the actual physical event with sufficient accuracy

- Models need to be validated by comparison with:
 - Plan A: the physical reality
 - But in many cases this is not feasible/ethical
 - Plan B: ex vivo dedicated experiment

Verification: determining if a numerical model obtained by discretizing a mathematical model of a physical event, and the code implementing it, represent the mathematical model with sufficient accuracy

(4) Model Validation
 Model validation is achieved by determining if the way we model a certain event or structure corresponds to the physical reality, with some tolerance. It is not always possible to measure something physical in the reality (e.g., you cannot break a patient bone to validate a model). Therefore, ex vivo or in vitro experiments can be designed to represent the challenges of the model are.

What is the difference between numerical models and experiments?

- They are both models of a more complex reality
- Their idealization is based on different paradigms:
 - Numerical models:
 - I can access reality only through idealization
 - Therefore it is more rigorous, as it is based on a theoretical approach (specimen, boundary conditions, materials, etc)
 - In vitro tests:
 - Include a fragment of the real world (the specimen)
 - Therefore, have a superior content of "real world"

	Numerical models	In vitro experiments
Specimen geometry	?	X
Material properties	?	X
Boundary conditions	?	?
Applied loads	?	?

(5) Numerical model vs experiments
 Experiments performed in a laboratory are a simplification of the reality, while numerical models are an idealization of the reality, as they contain different assumptions. For example, an ex vivo femur in the laboratory with the right material properties and the chosen loading conditions is not simulating a patient executing a motor task, it is a simplification.

How to design a proper validation experiment?

The numerical model and the ex vivo experiment must have:

- The same **geometry**
- The same **material properties**
- The same **loading conditions**
- The same **boundary conditions** (constraints)

In addition, we need:

- A number of **measurements** => transducers + registration
- The same **pose** => registration
- Quantitative comparison** between experiment and numerical models => metrics and stats

(6) Designing Validation experiments
 Same geometry, same material properties, same boundary and loading conditions are required. Comparison with generic models or literature data is doable but less reliable for the validation process. It is also required that the model is registered to the physical specimen, so that the numerical (virtual) model and the physical specimen are aligned and oriented the same way. Subsequently, one should identify the quantities that can be measured on both the physical and numerical specimen, as well as metrics to allow for a quantitative comparison of what is being measured (deformation, load, etc.)

3.1.4 [Module 3: Example cases](#)

Instructor

Giorgio Davico, Alma Mater Studiorum, University of Bologna, Italy.

Giulia Russo, University of Catania, Italy.

Objective

This course module provides the participants with two state-of-the-art examples of in silico medicine models that are in different stages of their development and have the perspective of being used in the clinical practice and/or the development of improved treatment strategies.

Learning Goals

After attending the lecture on "Example cases". participants should be able to:

...

Learning goals

- Illustrate the added value of in silico medicine with state-of-the-art examples;
- Link the general concepts related to in silico modeling to state-of-the-art examples;
- Summarize the state-of-the-art of in silico medicine in two different domains;
- Critically discuss the contribution of the presented in silico models to the clinical practice on the short-term.

Course material

Title: Example cases.

Duration : Example 1 (8m32sec) ; Example 2 (7m25 sec).

Date of creation: 2024-01-12.

A short overview of key slides and transcripts is illustrates the lecture on 'Example cases of In Silico Technologies'.

Example case 1A: Force Loss

Example case 1B: Force Loss

As we age, our muscles naturally tend to become weaker. Dynapenia is quite prevalent in the elderly population, and the numbers further increase in the presence of concurrent neuromuscular or musculoskeletal disorders and diseases. The main problem is that when a patient with dynapenia gets to the hospital to seek help, it is not easy and straightforward for the clinicians to identify the most appropriate clinical pathway.

A digital twin is in this case a virtual representation of the patients' musculoskeletal system, built from medical imaging data. Being a digital twin a computer model, it can be employed within a simulation framework to perform various tests in silico aimed to identify the primary cause for dynapenia. The ForceLoss solution is an in silico framework for the differential diagnosis for the loss of muscle force.

Example case 2A: Immune system simulator

Example case 2B: Immune system simulator

Universal immune system simulator for multiple sclerosis.

UISS-MS tool is a specialized version of our broader universal new system Simulator framework. It simulates immune system dynamics at cellular and molecular levels and is specifically tailored for multiple sclerosis. UISS MS is able to stratify by treatment a specific cohort of MS patients and to be used as an in silico trials of multiple sclerosis therapies.

UISS MS functions as a clinical decision support system addressing optimal treatments to slow disease progression in MS patients based on individual immunological profiles. We also use UISS-MS to conduct in silico trial. These aids in predicting the effects of new or existing drugs on virtual patients. Helping select dosages for phase two trials and predicting drug efficacy for phase three trials.

4 Outlook

The report introduced the various objectives of the ISW project, before situating the focus of this work to address the barrier around insufficiently informed stakeholders. The **introductory chapter sketched the critical role of healthcare professionals**. Further, some of the **gaps and challenges** around informing and empowering HCPs are highlighted. Subsequently, a series of **information packages (in chapter 2)** and **lecture materials (in chapter 3)** designed and delivered as part of WP5 and WP7 activities, addressed the gaps. These packages are meant to offer not only impactful information about in silico medicine and in silico technologies but also introduce HCPs to continuous education programs. Thus, these information packages offer the **opportunity to deepen their knowledge for professional practice**, whereby they strive to use and adopt in silico trial technologies

While some of the gaps are addressed through information packages and lecture materials, we acknowledge that other aspects are left unaddressed (e.g. policy, regulations, budget, reimbursement) They are still relevant for the adoption of in silico technologies by the clinical community, but not effectively dealt through these information packages for HCP. Indeed, these gaps are well captured during our stakeholder engagement activities and have been or are being documented through the ongoing work on policy and white paper related deliverables (D5.5, D5.7, D5.8) within the ISW consortium.

5 Acknowledgements

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6 Appendix

The following four appendix sections describes the preliminary work on identifying learning goals for in silico trials technologies:

- **Appendix 1:** A brief introduction to the methodology behind identification of learning goals and strategy to organize a test-session based on short mini-courses.
- **Appendix 2:** The proposed curricula with individual breakdown of the full-length accredited lectures.
- **Appendix 3:** The details of micro-skills for HCPs – students studying medicine & professionals.
- **Appendix 4:** Description of the learning platform

6.1 Appendix 1: Introduction to Lecture Material on In silico technologies

One of the many objectives of the In Silico World project is to focus on the (re-)training of technical and non-technical professionals on the use, opportunities and threats of in silico trials. Progress reports on ISW WP 7 Tasks 7.1-7.5 as well as Deliverable D7.1, presents the detailed description on the categorization of in silico technology stakeholders³⁵. Subsequently, the ISW consortium organized surveys, questionnaires and a consensus workshops, to identify the macro-level and micro-level learning goals for each of the stakeholder groups³⁶. In other words, the so-called **intended learning objectives (ILO)** as defined by '**statements of what a learner should know and be able to do at the end of a course element**'³⁷ were identified. They helped determine the skills and competencies the in silico technology workforce need to be trained or retrained for. Independent of training or retraining stream, the following macro-level in silico technology related ILO's were identified as key learning goals that all groups of stakeholders would strive to acquire on completion of in silico trial technology lectures.

Macro-level Intended Learning Objectives (ILO)

The following **six ILO's form the centrepiece of the definition of training or retraining curricula**, which are then broken down into numerous micro-level skills. Along the process, their relevance per stakeholder category was also identified. For extended reading on the learning goals associated with each stakeholder category, we refer the reader to the 'Proposal for curricula on in silico Trials'²².

H1. Apply the necessary preliminary technical and biomedical knowledge

These are the skills that students need to have as pre-requisite before they can receive the training targeting the skills listed in the other macro-skills. In most cases, they should be part of a previous degree (e.g., BS level) or of the foundational course of the current degree; however, in some cases,

³⁵ Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). A systematic approach to define intended learning outcomes for different stakeholders for in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8380239>

³⁶ Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400657>

³⁷ Greensted, Chris. "Intended learning outcomes." EFMD Global Focus 8.1 (2014): 20-25.

it might be necessary to include them in the curriculum a “Foundations on in silico medicine” module that fills some gaps.

H2. Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

This macro-skill addresses the need for practitioners to accurately and effectively inform those stakeholders with direct or indirect decisional power on the use of in silico methodologies.

H3. Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

This set of skills should enable the students to survey existing ethical, legal and regulatory frameworks and use them to define data management and to develop, validate and deploy in silico methodologies, including institutional review board (IRB) submissions and the pursuit of regulatory objectives.

H4. Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

Micro-skills required by anyone who needs to review, choose, and use in silico methodologies.

H5. Develop In Silico Methodologies

Skills required by practitioners of in silico methodologies that use them in the frame of a good simulation practice framework.

H6. Apply good simulation practice

The *good practice* are operational rules that usually emerge from a consensus process within a community of practice. However, in some cases they are formalised in voluntary or mandatory technical standards. As no standard exists yet for the **Good Simulation Practice**, we use as a basis the **position paper on the Good Simulation Practice**³⁸ developed by the In Silico World Community of Practice.

Course materials corresponding to ILO's

Detailed overview of learning goals, the corresponding course structure leading to ECTS credits have been well identified (See Appendix 2). Before expending resources to formulate full-length course content for greater than 3 ECTS, the ISW consortium envisaged to first start with a testing phase by offering mini-courses that require lighter preparations. The objective is to generate early momentum and interest for in silico technology course among the target audience, by quickly and effectively introducing fundamental concepts and practical applications. Thereby have a rapid head start but also collect valuable feedback and assess the effectiveness of the teaching methods.

WP7 members in collaboration with rest of the ISW consortium, championed the assimilation of course materials for mini-courses. To this end, mini-learning materials per stakeholder are carefully

³⁸ Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best practices for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products. In: Synthesis Lectures on Biomedical Engineering. Viceconti M. & Emili L. (Eds.), Springer Cham eBook. ISBN: 978-3-031-48283-0, 2024.

curated to comprehensively cover the full-coursework identified in Appendix 2. In other words, coherence with the six macro ILO's H1-H6, as well micro-skills from the originally identified learning goals of full-curriculum are preserved.

6.2 Appendix 2: Proposal of curricula for in silico technologies

The proposal of curricula outlined by ISW consortium, for

- Technical stakeholders 12 ECTS
 - Introduction to in silico medicine (6ECTS)
 - Computational Bioengineering (6ECTS)
- Non-Technical stakeholders 3 ECTS
 - Introduction to in silico medicine for non-engineers

Course 1: Introduction to in silico medicine (6ECTS)

L01 Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?
L02 From a clinical problem to a Digital Twin in Healthcare
L03 In silico medicine: ethical and legal considerations
L04 Regulatory and standardization aspects
L05 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro experimentation
L06 Examples of in silico medicine: reduction of animal experimentation
L07 Examples of in silico medicine: refinement of human experimentation
L08 In silico trials for medical devices
L09 In silico trials for medicinal products
L10 Communication in interdisciplinary settings
L11 Clinical applications of in silico medicine
L12 Industrial applications of in silico medicine

Table 1: Lectures for course 1 - 'Introduction to In Silico Medicine – 6 ECTS'

Course 2: Computational Bioengineering (6ECTS)

L01 Recalls of human pathophysiology
L02 Recalls of biophysics
L03 Recalls of biochemistry
L04 Recalls of numerical analysis
L05 Stochastic modelling
L06 Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part 1
L08 Development of a knowledge-driven digital twin in healthcare part 2
L09 Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part 1
L10 Development of a data-driven digital twin in healthcare part 2
L11 Development of in silico trials solutions
L12 Credibility of predictive models

Table 2: Lecturers for course 2-'Computational Bioengineering – 6 ECTS'

Course 3: Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers (3ECTS)

L01 Recall concepts of biostatistics
L02 Recall concepts of biostatistics
L03 Introduction to bioengineering part 1
L04 Introduction to bioengineering part 2
L05 Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?
L06 From a clinical problem to a Digital Twin in Healthcare
L07 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation
L08 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of in vitro, animal and human experimentation
L09 Clinical applications of In Silico Medicine
L10 In Silico Medicine: ethical and social considerations
L11 Communication in interdisciplinary settings
L12 Communication to patients

Table 3: Lectures for course 3 – ‘Introduction to IN Silico Medicine for non-engineers – 3ECTS’

6.3 Appendix 3: Learning goals of HCPs

HCPs are considered as subject matter experts in their profession, who are already employed in stakeholder organisations like hospitals, industry, regulatory agencies, (or) considered students undergoing formal education at academic institutions, to become future HCPs and work as employees at these stakeholder organisations. Further, two learning streams are foreseen:

For the training stream of healthcare professionals, two broad categories are identified.

- First, those pursuing bachelor-master-doctoral programs within the medical/clinical institutions
- Second, those pursuing master or advanced masters in allied health professions like medical imaging technologists, nursing, pharmacy, physiotherapy, etc.
- For example:
 - Biomedical Engineering (MS, PhD),
 - Medicine (BS, MS).
 - Life Science (BS, MS).
 - Allied Health Professions (MS).

The re-training stream considers all HCPs, both clinical and non-clinical health professionals within

- medical facilities (e.g. practising clinicians, technology assessment reviewers).
- industry (e.g. medical liaison, trainers of medical technologies).
- regulatory agencies (e.g. internal clinicians / clinical reviewers at notified bodies / regulators).
- health technology assessment (HTA) bodies (e.g. clinical experts, HTA committee members).
- For example:
 - Pre-competitive: Biomedical researchers

- Pre-competitive: Health technology researchers
- Pre-competitive: Pharmacology researchers
- Industry: Research and product development (R&D)
- Industry: Regulatory & Quality
- Governmental Agencies: Regulators staff
- Governmental Agencies: HTA staff

While the professional HCPs would benefit from re-training to upskill their professional practise for handling in silico trial technologies, the ‘to-be professionals’ HCPs, would require training or be formally educated a new.

6.3.1 Intended Learning objectives for HCPs

The list of learning objectives pertaining to HCPs, as identified within the WP7³⁹ are briefly summarized here. The list is not exhaustive and cover all the ILO’s that were determined, rather only those that qualified the ranking threshold, for which the curricula was developed.

³⁹ Vander Linden, K., Van Looy, G., Davico, G., Viceconti, M., & Vander Sloten, J. (2023). Proposal for curricula to train and retrain different stakeholders on in silico trials (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400657>

Skills and objectives for Master's in medicine

1.5. MS in Medicine

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the students should already possess these learning outcomes through previous degrees:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.2 Knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases
- H 1.3.4 Apply knowledge of cell biology to the understanding of the mechanisms of action of drugs

New module: Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H 1.4.1 Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.2 Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.3 Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H 1.4.4 Elaborate bio-signals and medical images
- H 2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H 2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H 2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs
- H 4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation

This module could be designed as a 3 ECTS module, with a total student commitment of 100 hours, of which 12 hours are frontal teaching, 12 hours are laboratory teaching, and the rest is personal study. The 12 one-hour lectures could include, for example, the following:

- M4-L01 Recall concepts of biostatistics (H 1.3.5, H 1.1.7)
- M4-L02 Recall concepts of biostatistics (H 1.3.5, H 1.1.7)
- M4-L03 Introduction to bioengineering part 1 (H 1.4.1, H 1.4.2, H 1.4.3, H 1.4.4)
- M4-L04 Introduction to bioengineering part 2 (H 1.4.1, H 1.4.2, H 1.4.3, H 1.4.4)
- M4-L05 Introduction to in silico medicine: can nature be predicted?

- M4-L06 From a clinical problem to a Digital Twin in Healthcare (H2.1)
- M4-L07 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro*, animal and human experimentation (H4.1)
- M4-L08 Examples of in silico medicine: replacement of *in vitro*, animal and human experimentation (H4.1)
- M4-L09 Clinical applications of In Silico Medicine (H2.12)
- M4-L10 In Silico Medicine: ethical and social considerations (H2.5, H2.6)
- M4-L11 Communication in interdisciplinary settings (H2.2)
- M4-L12 Communication to patients (H2.8)

Skills and objectives for Master's in allied profession (e.g. imaging technologists)

1.6. MS in Allied Health Professions

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the students should already possess these learning outcomes through previous degrees:

- H 1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.2 Knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H 1.3.3 Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases

Inclusions in the module Introduction to In Silico Medicine for non-engineers

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H 1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments
- H 2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H 2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H 2.8 Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H 2.12 Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

Skills and objectives for Governmental agency – Health Technology assessment stream

2.7 Governmental agencies –health technology assessment bodies staff

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the staff should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.2 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant legislation
- H3.4 Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
 - H3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
 - H3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
 - H3.4.3 Use the understanding of the emerging legislation, standards, and guidelines on Artificial Intelligence

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.1 Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H4.2 Conduct a critical review (SWOT analysis) of adopting different in silico methodologies to address an unmet need
- H4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report

Skills and objectives for Governmental agency – Regulatory stream

2.8 Governmental agencies – regulators staff

Pre-requisites

All experts agree that the staff should already possess these learning outcomes. Depending on their background, the learning outcomes can be recalled and are included in the SPOC *Introductory modules Math & Statistics, Biomedicine, Bioengineering and Computer Science*.

- H 1.1.1 Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H 1.1.3 Define and review differential equations
- H 1.1.5 Define and review optimisation problems
- H 1.1.7 Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data
- H1.3.1 Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.5 Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design and analysis of clinical experiments

Inclusion in SPOC module: Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H2.1 Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2 Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3 Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5 Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.6 Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication

Inclusion in SPOC module: Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H3.1 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.2 Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant legislation
- H3.4 Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
 - H3.4.1 Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
 - H3.4.2 Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
 - H3.4.3 Use the understanding of the emerging legislation, standards, and guidelines on Artificial Intelligence
- H3.6 Use the knowledge of EU and US regulatory systems for medical products to achieve specific regulatory objectives
 - H3.6.1 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the regulatory qualification of in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.2 Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the marketing authorisation for in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.3 Use regulatory knowledge to implement a total lifecycle-based framework for AI-based in silico methodologies

Inclusion in SPOC module: Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

In terms of ILOs, these are necessary:

- H4.11 Critically review a credibility assessment report

6.4 Appendix 4: e-Learning platform

The learning materials of mini-courses are currently offered in a moderated self-learning online platform – [Toledo Ultra Community portal](#). Access to the lecture materials, can be facilitated by contacting the ISW project communication team (info@insilico.world) or by directly contacting the responsible project partner – KU Leuven MECH:

- Lise Gheysen (lise.gheysen@kuleuven.be).

The platform includes

- A **self-assign and self-assessment tool** to evaluate the participants’ prior knowledge,
 - The self-assign tool allows the participants to self-assign themselves to a stakeholder group and training level (beginner or retraining).
 - The self-assessment tool helps one to identify their skill level and to refresh or refine their knowledge if needed.
- **Pre-evaluation questionnaire** to capture the baseline of participant’s understanding of In Silico Medicine.
- **Overview of modules**
 - With objectives and learning goals.
- Learning materials
 - **Slides materials in PDF format.**
 - **Recording of the coursework**, with video and voice over.
 - **Transcription** of the instructor.
- Post-evaluation questionnaire to capture any discernible differences in the knowledge of participants.

6.4.1 [Toledo User guide - How to enrol and access](#)

A step-by-step guide with illustration of the graphical user interface of the e-learning platform are explained, in this section.

Step-by-step procedure to enrol and access lecture materials

TOLEDO USER GUIDE	
	<p>Step 1. Request access to KU Leuven team. To do so, please send an email to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - info@insilico.world

	<p>- Lise Gheysen lise.gheysen@kuleuven.be</p> <p>On receiving the approval to access, go to step 1 to activate the profile</p>
	<p>Step 2. Create and activate your account.</p>
	<p>Step 3. Login to Toledo with your credentials.</p>
	<p>Step 3a. Click the In Silico World panel.</p>

Step 3b.
Knowledge check before assigning to a group.

Step 4.
Click on Assign yourself to a group.

Step 5.
Join a group, click "X" button to go back to main page.

Step 6.
Click on the "In Silico World" course material. All the available modules will appear in the drop-down menu. Click on the one of your interests.

Step 7.
After a brief introduction and a pre-course questionnaire you will be able to now start the course.

Step 8.
Video lectures and visual materials are available throughout the course.

Note: you can pause and start a new course at any time.

